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On Advancing Internationalization of Thai Higher Education: Voices of Foreign Faculty Members

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Abstract

Employing foreign faculty members (FFMs) is one of the strategic internationalization efforts of Thai higher education institutions (HEIs). This qualitative study explored the roles and challenges of 13 volunteer FFMs while advancing internationalization efforts within their Thai HEIs. After a reflexive thematic analysis of qualitative data collected from open-ended surveys and semi-structured interviews, the research identified key themes in their roles: offering practical insights, facilitating collaborative partnerships, emphasizing professional development, ensuring adherence to quality standards, and promoting cultural exchange and inclusivity. The study also explicated themes on complexities of interpersonal dynamics between FFMs and their local and international colleagues, the adoption of new teaching frameworks, and the impact of language proficiency dilemmas on curriculum delivery. This study highlights the critical contributions of FFMs in shaping the internationalization agenda and enhancing the global competitiveness of Thai HEIs. Furthermore, the study accentuates the importance of fostering a supportive and inclusive academic environment, promoting intercultural understanding, and balancing global perspectives with local cultural sensitivities. Future research directions and implications on Thai HEIs and beyond are offered.

Keywords: *internationalization, foreign faculty members, Thai higher education institutions*

Introduction

Internationalization (IZN) has become a transformative force in the global educational landscape due to its profound impact on educational practices, policies, and outcomes on a global scale. IZN has then driven higher education institutions (HEIs) to pursue continuous improvement and foster a more inclusive and dynamic educational ecosystem (Alsharari, 2018). In accordance with Knight's (2012) description, IZN is the process of integrating an international, intercultural, or global dimension into the purpose, functions, and delivery of post-secondary or higher education. Thus, HEIs have been moved to shape a global outlook by enhancing the quality and relevance of higher education so that students can thrive in an increasingly interconnected world (Altbach & Knight, 2007; Knight, 2018).

Propelled to take part in IZN, HEIs worldwide have actively engaged by putting in strategic efforts in several ways. For instance, Heitor (2015) explains that HEIs are forming alliances with foreign universities to foster student and faculty exchanges, promote joint research initiatives, and enhance their academic capabilities and global visibility. Additionally, as explained in an Omani study by Hubais and Muftahu (2022) and a Russian study by Makeeva and Lopukhova (2018), HEIs have been observed to have demonstrated approaches to integrating global perspectives into their curricula by including international or cross-cultural content within existing courses. There are also efforts to hire faculty members from different countries and cultural backgrounds to provide students with a more diverse and inclusive education (Alsharari, 2018; Romani-Dias & Carneiro, 2020).

Furthermore, participation in international accreditation and university rankings further solidifies their commitment to participate in IZN (De Wit, 2019; Hauptman Komotar, 2019; Stukalova et al., 2015). These moves provide external validation of HEIs' quality and standards while allowing them to benchmark themselves against peer institutions globally and identify areas for improvement (Johnes, 2018; Olcay & Bulu, 2017). Knight (2016) has also discussed that HEIs have embraced transnational education as a strategic approach to IZN, which refers to delivering educational programs and qualifications across national borders through various modes of delivery, such as branch campuses, joint or dual degree programs, online learning, and franchising arrangements.

Amidst the comprehensive efforts of HEIs to participate in IZN, faculty members (FMs) have emerged as integral factors for several reasons. One reason is their active involvement in international faculty mobility, exemplified by their movement between countries, as highlighted by Bedenlier (2017). Moreover, FMs actively engage in collaborative research projects with international partners, contributing to the advancement of knowledge on a global scale, as shown in the study of Criswell and Zhu (2015), which explored the role of FMs in the United States and Canada, portraying them as crucial agents driving internationalization efforts. They highlighted faculty's strong commitment to advancing teaching and research, participation in international organizations, and engagement in professional conferences. Meanwhile, studies have also delineated that FMs play a critical role in shaping students' attitudes, values, and behaviors. Through their mentorship and guidance, they have the potential to inspire students to become engaged global citizens. Renfors (2021) conducted a study in Finland that emphasized FMs as central figures responsible for integrating inclusive curriculum content and relevant insights into their teaching practices, aligning with students' future professions. Moreover, studies by Ndaipa et al. (2023) in Mozambique and Sibawaihi and Fernandes (2023) in Indonesia have underscored FMs' efforts in advancing internationalization. Similarly, In the Philippine context, Ulla and Tarrayo (2021) examined the contributions of FMs (referred to as 'academics' in their study) and found that FMs play a vital role in internationalizing teaching and research through their academic and community services. Thus, with these studies, FMs can be considered catalysts for internationalizing higher education.

While numerous studies have delved into the roles of FMs and their involvement in internationalization efforts, scant attention has been directed toward exploring the participation of foreign faculty members (FFMs) in the internationalization process. In this study, FFMs are individuals recruited from overseas to work as educators or researchers in HEIs (e.g., an American professional working in a Thai HEI). Records show that HEIs have been strategically hiring FFMs as part of their internationalization efforts, driven by the recognition that a diverse faculty body contributes to the globalization of the institution and prepares students for success in an increasingly interconnected world (Alsharari, 2018; Romani-Dias & Carneiro, 2020).

In the context of Thailand, the country has been actively recruiting foreign faculty members to teach various subjects, primarily focusing on English as a foreign language in HEIs (Methanonphakhun & Deocampo, 2016; Ulla, 2018). This initiative reflects Thailand's commitment to internationalizing its higher education sector by incorporating global perspectives, enhancing language proficiency, and fostering cross-cultural understanding among students and faculty members (Snodin et al., 2021). Moreover, with Thailand 4.0 Policy (a national economic strategy that emphasizes the importance of innovation, technology, and human capital development to drive economic growth and competitiveness), HEIs have been propelled to internationalize their programs, collaborate with global partners, and equip students with the skills needed for success in the digital age (Buasuwan, 2018). This implies that the recruitment of FFMs forms a crucial component of this IZN strategy in Thai HEIs.

With the desire to address the gap, this study has been conceived. This exploratory-descriptive qualitative study aims to explore the voices (i.e., their roles, challenges, and coping practices) of FFMs within Thai universities, a context rarely given attention to in the current body of literature. We believe in the imperative of recognizing their voices and efforts because, despite their status as outsiders to the country, they have demonstrated contributions to the internationalization endeavors of the HEIs they serve. The insights gained can inform policy development and institutional practices of the HEIs within and beyond this study regarding strategies and support mechanisms to better integrate and empower this important demographic within their academic communities. Lastly, this study can contribute to the broader body of literature on higher education internationalization. By shedding light on an underexplored area, the study can stimulate further research and dialogue on the roles, experiences, and contributions of FFMs to the internationalization agenda.

Research Questions

1. What roles do foreign faculty members (FFMs) undertake within Thai higher education institutions (HEIs) to advance internationalization efforts?
2. What are the main challenges encountered by FFMs in their roles within Thai HEIs, and how do they navigate them?

Methodology

This study employed an exploratory-descriptive qualitative design of Hunter et al. (2019), an approach combining elements of exploratory research, which seeks to investigate a topic when little is known about it, and descriptive research, which aims to describe the characteristics of a phenomenon or population. This design allowed researchers to explore a relatively uncharted territory, such as the roles and challenges of FFMs in Thai HEIs regarding the internationalization of education.

Thirteen foreign lecturers currently teaching in Thai HEIs participated in this study. Creswell and Poth (2018) suggested that sample sizes in qualitative research can be small, often ranging from 5 to 25 participants, depending on the study's purpose and the methodology used. For this study, participants were recruited through a call for participants posted on various social media platforms, including WhatsApp, Facebook groups, LinkedIn, Twitter, and Instagram. The inclusion criteria specified that participants must be actively teaching in a Thai higher education institution for at least one year, possess an understanding of the internationalization of education, and have experience participating in internationalization efforts within their institution. Interested individuals registered for the study through a provided link and were subsequently screened for eligibility.

Certain exclusion criteria were applied to maintain the study's focus and relevance. Faculty members who had been employed at their Thai HEI for less than one year were excluded, as they might not have had adequate experience to provide meaningful insights into the internationalization processes. Additionally, local Thai faculty members were excluded to maintain the focus on the experiences of FFMs. Participants who were not actively engaged in any form of internationalization activities within their institution were also excluded, as their input would not directly address the research questions.

Participants had the right to withdraw from the study at any point without any repercussions. Withdrawal criteria included any indication of discomfort or unwillingness to continue participation, which was respected immediately upon expression. Furthermore, if any participant's circumstances changed in a way that would significantly affect their ability to contribute relevant information (e.g., leaving the institution or moving to a non-internationalization-related role), they were provided the option to withdraw. Data from participants who chose to withdraw was not included in the final analysis to ensure ethical standards and the integrity of the study.

The participants' ages ranged from 27 to 56, with varying degrees of teaching experience in Thai HEIs, ranging from less than 2 years

to 6 years. In terms of gender, three males, six females, and three LGBTQI+ individuals participated, with one participant opting not to disclose their gender. Nationalities represented include Filipino, Russian, Indonesian, and American. Educational backgrounds vary, with participants holding a range of qualifications from bachelor's degrees to PhDs or EdDs. Additionally, one participant was employed in a private HEI, and the rest were in public HEIs.

Prior to data collection, informed consent was obtained from each participant. They were guaranteed confidentiality through the assignment of pseudonyms, denoted as FFM1 to FFM13, where FFM means foreign faculty member. Furthermore, participants were clearly informed of their right to withdraw from the study at any juncture without incurring any repercussions.

Data were collected through an open-ended qualitative survey sent to the email addresses provided by each participant in the preliminary survey. The survey comprised questions aimed at eliciting participants' narratives and experiences of participating in internationalization efforts within their institution. For example, to address RQ1, the study posed several questions to the participants. These included inquiries about their primary responsibilities at their Thai HEI and their perceptions of their role in advancing the institution's internationalization agenda. Participants were also asked about their contributions to collaborative partnerships or international research initiatives, the incorporation of global or cross-cultural perspectives into their teaching and curriculum, and any specific projects or programs they had been involved in that aimed to promote internationalization. For RQ2, participants were questioned about the challenges they encountered while working in their Thai HEI, particularly how language barriers affected their teaching and interactions with colleagues and students. They were also asked to describe any cultural differences they experienced and how they navigated these differences. Additionally, the study explored the support mechanisms or resources that participants found helpful in overcoming challenges and whether any institutional policies or practices had facilitated or hindered their role in advancing internationalization. Participants were encouraged to provide detailed responses to each question. Following the completion of the survey, follow-up online interviews were conducted with participants who indicated their willingness to participate in further discussions. Participants who expressed their consent for follow-up interviews during the survey were contacted to schedule online interview sessions.

The data analysis process followed a reflexive thematic analysis approach (Braun & Clarke, 2019). Firstly, all survey responses and interview transcripts were carefully reviewed and organized. Then, initial codes were generated based on recurring themes, patterns, and key concepts emerging from the data. Subsequently, these initial codes were systematically grouped into broader themes and subthemes through an iterative process. Connections between themes were explored, and any discrepancies or divergent perspectives were noted for further examination.

Three external researchers independently reviewed the analysis. Additionally, member checking was employed to validate the interpretation of participants' responses. Participants were provided with summaries of their survey responses and interview transcripts, and their feedback was sought to confirm the accuracy and interpretation of their data. Throughout the analysis, reflexivity was maintained, with researchers continuously reflecting on their own biases and preconceptions to ensure that the findings remained grounded in the data.

Results and Discussion

Roles of FFMs' IZN Involvement in Thai HEIs

The responses gathered from both the open-ended survey and the subsequent semi-structured online interviews underwent thorough analysis, revealing findings that delineate the roles FFMs undertake within Thai HEIs to advance internationalization efforts. The following themes emerged:

Offering practical insights. According to the participants, they have a crucial role in providing practical insights derived from their personal experiences and practices. By sharing their firsthand knowledge of implementing global initiatives within diverse cultural contexts, they contribute to understanding the challenges and opportunities associated with internationalization. Their insights aid in determining effective strategies and approaches for advancing these initiatives.

As a foreign faculty member actively engaged in internationalization efforts within our institution, I firmly believe that my insights are crucial for the success of our endeavors in this domain. Drawing from my experiences and practices accumulated over the past five years of working with diverse cultures, I offer a unique perspective that enriches our approach to internationalization. My experiences have taught me the importance of cultivating a supportive and inclusive learning environment that values diversity and promotes intercultural understanding. By fostering mutual respect and empathy among students and faculty members, we can create opportunities for meaningful cross-cultural exchanges and collaboration. (FFM1)

From my own experience with international projects in higher education, I've gained valuable insights into what works and what doesn't. Working closely with students from different backgrounds and partnering with people from around the world has taught me a lot about different cultures. (FFM3)

Facilitating collaborative partnerships. Collaboration was highlighted by the participants as essential for driving internationalization efforts. FFMs emphasized the significance of collaborating with students, colleagues, and international partners. Through collaborative

partnerships, they claimed to gain diverse perspectives and innovative approaches, which enhance the effectiveness of implementing internationalization initiatives. These partnerships foster a culture of cooperation and knowledge exchange, enriching the educational experiences within HEIs.

Collaborative partnerships are crucial for internationalization efforts. By working together with students, colleagues, and international partners, we gain diverse perspectives, practical insights, and innovative approaches, enhancing the effectiveness of implementation. (FFM6)

Through my participation in collaborative research projects and interdisciplinary collaborations, I contribute to a deeper understanding of internationalization. Engaging in dialogue with colleagues from diverse disciplinary backgrounds and cultural perspectives fosters a culture of cooperation and knowledge exchange within HEIs. (FFM12)

Partnerships with international universities have shown me the power of cultural exchange in enriching students' educational experiences. My goal is to foster an inclusive and globally-minded learning environment through collaboration with students and colleagues. (FFM10)

Emphasizing professional development. FFMs have also described the importance of ongoing learning and development in addressing the complexities of internationalization. By engaging in professional development activities and collaborating with colleagues from diverse backgrounds, they can stay updated on emerging trends and best practices. To them, their commitment to continuous learning contributes to more informed and effective implementation of internationalization efforts. This to them can ensure the quality and relevance of educational practices within their HEIs.

Engagement in continuing professional development and collaboration with colleagues from diverse nationalities enhances our understanding of internationalization. By staying abreast of emerging trends and best practices, we contribute to more informed and effective implementation. (FFM11)

My participation in professional development activities and interdisciplinary collaborations underscores the interconnected nature of internationalization. Through ongoing learning, we cultivate a culture of global citizenship and intercultural competence within HEIs. (FFM12)

Ensuring adherence to quality standards. FFMs have also mentioned that another role they take is to prioritize adherence to international quality standards to enhance the credibility and effectiveness of internationalization efforts. By ensuring they follow the United Kingdom Professional Standards Framework (UKPSF) framework, FFMs believe they can demonstrate their commitment to meeting international benchmarks. They believe that this dedication to maintaining high-quality educational practices contributes to the reputation and competitiveness of their HEIs on the global stage.

As a foreign faculty member, I have a responsibility to ensure that my teaching practices align with international standards to enhance the credibility and effectiveness of our institution's internationalization efforts. By staying informed about best practices and quality benchmarks, I can contribute to the overall reputation and competitiveness of our HEIs on the global stage. (FFM4)

I am deeply committed to upholding the highest standards of quality and rigor in my teaching practices. To achieve this, I apply the principles outlined in the UKPSF framework to guide my pedagogical approach. By aligning my teaching methodologies with this internationally recognized standard, I strive to provide my students with an exceptional learning experience. (FFM10)

Promoting cultural exchange and inclusivity. FFMs also recognized the transformative power of cultural exchange in enriching educational experiences and fostering a globally-minded learning environment. In their statements, they shared that they actively promote inclusivity and diversity within academic communities by incorporating global perspectives and language learning opportunities into the curriculum. To them, these efforts contribute to preparing students for success in a globalized world and fostering an inclusive learning environment that celebrates cultural diversity.

Through my work as an English Language lecturer, I've witnessed firsthand the importance of incorporating global perspectives and language learning opportunities into the curriculum. My experiences organizing events and partnering with international universities have shown me the power of cultural exchange in enriching students' educational experiences. Ultimately, my goal is to foster an inclusive and globally-minded learning environment where students can thrive. (FFM6)

My unique perspective as a non-native English speaker from the Philippines allows me to offer insights into the challenges and opportunities faced by individuals from diverse linguistic and cultural backgrounds in the internationalization process. By sharing my own experiences of navigating language barriers, cultural differences, and interpersonal dynamics, I shed light on the complexities inherent in fostering a truly inclusive and globally-minded academic community. (FFM8)

These roles collectively highlight the multifaceted contributions of FFMs in advancing internationalization efforts within Thai HEIs. By offering practical insights, facilitating collaborative partnerships, emphasizing professional development, ensuring adherence to quality standards, and promoting cultural exchange and inclusivity, FFMs play important roles in shaping the internationalization agenda and enhancing the global competitiveness of HEIs.

Challenges of FFMs' IZN Involvement in Thai HEIs

Interpersonal dynamics with colleagues. The data also reveals that amid their involvement in IZN in Thai HEIs, participants have discussed their challenges and shared their strategies to overcome them. The first theme focuses on the challenges they experience in collaborating with their colleagues in Thai HEIs, referring to how they communicate with local and other foreign lecturers. For example, the differences in culture and language exacerbate this challenge, thus:

Many local lecturers find it difficult to speak in English... To address this challenge, I've prioritized clear communication with local faculty and staff, and there should be mutual understanding and respect for diverse opinions. (FFM1)

Other participants also shared the same sentiment. For them to address this, they strive to be respectful and open to continuous learning:

...learn about and respect Thai culture, and be sensitive to cultural nuances... Continuous personal development in intercultural communication can help in navigating these differences. (FFM2)

For me, the best way to address this issue is to respect the locals and find common ground that could work for everyone. (FFM5)

FFM12 was also specific in mentioning that not only because foreign lecturers have diverse socio-cultural and pedagogical backgrounds that contribute to challenges in IZN in Thai HEIs, but rather it is aggravated by the sense of entitlement or superiority of other native speakers.

One major issue is the belief that some of my native English-speaking colleagues have that they are more proficient in language and pedagogy than non-native English speakers...like our Line chat group being overrun with complaints about course materials and speakers interrupting sessions to correct spelling or grammar. It is ironic that they declined an invitation to be involved in the creation of these materials. But after using the materials for a while, they give a lot of criticism, at times even casting doubt on the authors' and developers' abilities. Some of them communicate with the department head with haughtiness. Many of them lack good decorum, yet I know it's crucial to avoid generalizing. (FFM12)

As FFM12 asserted, this mindset makes it difficult for them to work together effectively and leads to the undervaluing or dismissing of the contributions non-native English teachers make to the curriculum's internationalization efforts. With that, FL9 suggests that being open-minded to these differences can be helpful in dealing with them, and there must be opportunities for professional development and collaboration among faculty members.

Taking up a new framework for teaching and learning. Participants have noted that their university's ongoing commitment toward IZN has led to continuous changes, particularly in the approach to teaching English as a foreign language. For instance, FFM4 mentioned experiencing this firsthand when their department implemented the Optimal Input Theory in their classes. As a result, revisions were made to the course syllabi, materials, textbooks, and teaching methodologies to align with this new approach.

In our department... we're all about using the best strategies to help our students learn English better. One thing we do is use stories a lot in our classes. Stories aren't just entertaining; they're great for learning, too. When we use stories, we create a more immersive learning experience. We want our students to pick up new words and phrases naturally, just like they would in real-life situations. Plus, stories help students think critically and learn about different cultures. This is actually new for us here.. I mean, the application of this theory... (FFM4)

She concludes that the ongoing experimentation and development of classroom teaching strategies and techniques can sometimes feel overwhelming. The key to coping, she suggests, is to maintain flexibility and adaptability in response to the evolving policies and circumstances. In this regard, FFM2 has something to purport:

Dealing with the administrative and policy-related aspects of the university can be complex, with all changes, especially for someone unfamiliar with the system. So, building a network of supportive colleagues and administrators within the institution can provide guidance and assistance.

Alongside these changes in adopting a new framework, other participants also highlighted the challenge posed by faculty members who resist changes to the curriculum. For example, for FL3, overcoming this resistance requires effective communication, collaboration, and support mechanisms to address faculty concerns and facilitate a smooth transition and understanding.

Thai HEIs: An inheritor of language proficiency dilemmas. It is worth mentioning that participants have encountered challenges not only in navigating their professional relationships with co-lecturers and adapting to new frameworks but also in grappling with the reality of their university students' low proficiency levels. Despite expectations for students to attain at least a B1 level in accordance with the CEFR standards, participants have found themselves tasked with instructing students who are below A2 proficiency. This discrepancy, for them, presents significant hurdles in effectively implementing a curriculum delivered in English at the university. The reason behind this, according to FFM7:

Students are taught first to write and grammar, but never to speak or ask questions. The students in regular programs are never exposed to an English environment nor to an English culture. The students in regular programs are taught English to pass the exams. Never a critical thinking or involvement in English.

Like FFM7, FFM10 and FFM13 shared that in their efforts to globalize the curriculum at Thai HEIs, they encountered hurdles such as language barriers and student hesitation towards learning English. Nevertheless, to address these challenges:

I offer extra language help through workshops and one-on-one tutoring. I also spice up classes with interactive activities to make learning fun. Encouraging students to join cultural exchanges, even if they're not confident in English, helps us build a welcoming community. (FFM10)

I use different teaching methods like visuals, extra materials, and group activities to make sure everyone can understand and join in. For example, I use charts, videos, and simple readings to help explain things. I also organize group discussions and role-plays to encourage everyone to take part and practice their language skills. (FFM13)

Moreover, FFM11 brought up his involvement in a volunteer initiative where he assists students in practicing their English skills outside of the traditional classroom environment.

We have this "chatterbox cafe," an initiative offered by our department for all students. Here, students can engage in casual and enjoyable conversations in English with foreign English lecturers from the department. Although some students initially feel shy, they gradually become more comfortable and confident in practicing English in this supportive environment. (FFM11)

Globalizing local, localizing global. Based on the analysis, another challenge for the participants is in terms of striking a balance between global perspectives and local culture. In particular, FFM13, for example, emphasized the importance of ensuring that the curriculum they implement should resonate with Thai students while also exposing them to diverse viewpoints from around the world.

I have to find the right balance between global ideas and local culture. It's important for the curriculum to relate to Thai students while still showing them different viewpoints from around the world. (FFM13)

For her, to address this challenge, lecturers should closely collaborate with local and foreign colleagues to integrate cultural elements that Thai students can relate to, thus enriching their learning experience.

FFM11 also explained how this challenge in their department was addressed:

So, we have conducted in-depth curriculum analyses and needs assessments in order to solve this difficulty. We have been able to identify particular domains where internationalization can improve current frameworks without sacrificing cultural integrity thanks to these evaluations. We have communication with stakeholders, such as professors, students, and community representatives, to make sure that our learning objectives and the varied needs of our students are in line. (FFM11)

FM2 suggests that gradually introducing new pedagogical strategies can enrich the learning environment, allowing for the infusion of innovative techniques and global perspectives. FM2 thinks that this dual strategy not only respects the local context but also promotes an incremental shift towards a more internationalized curriculum that will result in both stability and progressive enhancement in educational practices.

To strictly implement is to risk my job. A notable finding from the analysis is that participants find it challenging to fully implement international standards for assessing and providing feedback on students, as outlined in the Common European Framework of Reference (CEFR). While they support the university's goal of internationalizing assessment standards, especially for evaluating English proficiency, they worry about being too harsh on students with lower proficiency levels. They fear that being too strict might lead to student frustration and, ultimately, lower teacher evaluation scores at the end of the term. This is concerning for foreign lecturers because evaluation scores determine contract renewals, as explained in the sample extract from one participant:

The primary challenge I have personally experienced when I imposed what I thought is best for them to learn the target language, but the result was horrible which solely lies in the repercussions of student evaluations, which significantly influence my teaching assessments and, consequently, jeopardize contract renewals. (FFM6)

Continuing, FFM6 noted the challenge of hesitating as a lecturer to rigorously implement academic standards, apprehensive that doing so might jeopardize his contract security. As suggested by FFM11:

We have to be friendly and careful about the words we use... Let them feel that we come from a space of concern... We need to provide culturally sensitive feedback that acknowledges students' efforts and achievements while identifying areas for growth that have fostered a supportive learning environment where students feel valued and motivated to succeed. (FFM11)

The findings in this study revealed the diverse roles played by FFMs within HEIs in advancing efforts towards internationalization. Initially, FFMs offer practical insights gleaned from their personal experiences, aiding in understanding the challenges and opportunities associated with internationalization. Subsequently, they facilitate collaborative partnerships with students, colleagues, and international counterparts to enrich initiatives with diverse perspectives and enhance their effectiveness. Furthermore, FFMs stress the importance of ongoing professional development in effectively navigating the complexities of internationalization. They also prioritize adherence to international quality standards to bolster the global credibility of HEIs. Lastly, FFMs actively promote cultural exchange and inclusivity within academic communities, equipping students for success in a globalized world. These findings corroborate the findings of previous studies (e.g., Bedenlier, 2017; Criswell & Zhu, 2015; Renfors, 2021; Sibawaihi & Fernandes,

2023) that have emphasized the big role of FMs in internationalization efforts within HEIs, encompassing active involvement in international faculty mobility, engagement in collaborative research projects, shaping students' attitudes, values, and behaviors, integration of inclusive curriculum content, and contributions to internationalizing teaching and research. While there is overlap in the roles highlighted for FMs and FFMs, such as engagement in collaborative partnerships and commitment to professional development, this study accentuates FFMs' perception of themselves as providers of practical insights derived from personal experiences, crucial for understanding challenges and opportunities related to internationalization. Moreover, FFMs are also instrumental in fostering collaborative partnerships and promoting cultural exchange and inclusivity within academic communities. This emphasis on the roles of FFMs within Thai HEIs reinforces the importance of faculty involvement in internationalization efforts, and thus be supported. As Niehaus and Williams (2015) have concluded, when faculty members are well supported, they can “develop the knowledge, perspectives, and motivation to engage in the difficult and important work” (p. 73).

Moreover, the data reveals the complex interpersonal dynamics FFMs navigate within Thai HEIs, particularly concerning their relationships with local and other foreign colleagues. Challenges in communication and collaboration arise due to cultural and linguistic differences, impacting both intra- and inter-departmental interactions. Despite these challenges, FFMs strive to foster understanding, respect, and inclusivity within academic communities while balancing global perspectives with local cultural sensitivities. These findings on FFMs' challenges resonate with existing literature on dynamics in multicultural workplaces. For example, Lonsmann's (2014) study in Denmark explained how varying language competencies among employees in an international company can lead to sociolinguistic exclusion, with international employees often proficient in the company's lingua franca but lacking skills in the local language, while some local employees may lack proficiency in the corporate language, typically English. In the same way, according to Dale-Olsen and Finseraas (2020), cultural diversity has the potential to enhance productivity by introducing fresh perspectives and fostering innovation. However, they argue that linguistic diversity, while valuable in many respects, may also pose challenges by increasing communication costs, thus potentially diminishing overall productivity within a diverse workplace environment.

This study's findings imply that fostering a supportive and inclusive environment, promoting intercultural understanding, and addressing faculty concerns are essential for overcoming barriers to internationalization. Moreover, the need for a balance between global perspectives and local cultural sensitivities is a significant factor in contextualizing internationalization initiatives to meet Thai students and academic communities' unique needs. In general, these findings then highlight the critical role of FFMs in driving internationalization efforts while advocating for policies and practices that support their professional development and well-being within Thai HEIs.

Conclusions

This research explored and described the multifaceted roles and challenges faced by foreign faculty members (FFMs) in advancing internationalization efforts within Thai higher education institutions (HEIs). Through an analysis of qualitative data, several key themes emerged, highlighting the importance of offering practical insights, facilitating collaborative partnerships, emphasizing professional development, ensuring adherence to quality standards, promoting cultural exchange and inclusivity, navigating interpersonal dynamics with colleagues, adopting new frameworks for teaching and learning, grappling with language proficiency dilemmas, and balancing global perspectives with local culture. These findings contribute to the existing literature by providing insights into the specific challenges and strategies employed by FFMs within the context of Thai HEIs. This study also highlights the importance of addressing cultural and linguistic barriers, fostering collaboration and understanding among faculty members, and promoting inclusive practices within academic communities.

Moving forward, it is imperative for Thai HEIs to recognize the vital role of FFMs in driving internationalization efforts and to implement policies and practices that support their professional development and well-being. This study stands to conclude that by cultivating an environment characterized by supportiveness and inclusivity, bolstering intercultural competence, and attentively addressing the concerns of faculty members, including those originating from foreign backgrounds, HEIs in Thailand and beyond are poised to augment their global competitiveness and equip students for triumph in an ever more interconnected global landscape.

Further research in this area could delve into the longitudinal effects of the strategies implemented by foreign faculty members in Thai HEIs on student outcomes, faculty satisfaction, and institutional reputation. Also, comparative studies across different contexts and geographical regions could offer a broader perspective on the roles and experiences of foreign faculty members in advancing internationalization efforts within higher education institutions worldwide.

References

- Alsharari, N. M. (2018). Internationalization of the higher education system: an interpretive analysis. *International Journal of Educational Management*, 32(3), 359-381.
- Altbach, P. G., & Knight, J. (2007). *Journal of Studies in International Education*, 11(3/4), 290-305.
- Bedenlier, S. (2017). Internationalization within higher education and its influence on faculty: experiences of Turkish academic staff. *Journal of Research in International Education*, 16(2), 185-196.

- Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2019). Reflecting on reflexive thematic analysis. *Qualitative research in sport, exercise and health*, 11(4), 589-597.
- Buasawan, P. (2018). Rethinking Thai higher education for Thailand 4.0. *Asian Education and Development Studies*, 7(2), 157-173.
- Creswell, J. W., & Poth, C. N. (2018). *Qualitative inquiry & research design: Choosing among five approaches* (Fourth edition.). Sage.
- Criswell, J. R., & Zhu, H. (2015). Faculty Internationalization Priorities. In *FIRE: Forum for International Research in Education* (Vol. 2, No. 2, pp. 22-39). Lehigh University Library and Technology Services, 8A East Packer Avenue, Fairchild Martindale Library Room 514, Bethlehem, PA 18015.
- Dale-Olsen, H., & Finseraas, H. (2020). Linguistic diversity and workplace productivity. *Labour Economics*, 64, 101813.
- De Wit, H. (2019). Internationalization in higher education, a critical review. *SFU Educational Review*, 12(3), 9-17.
- Garson, K. (2016). Reframing internationalization. *Canadian Journal of Higher Education*, 46(2), 19-39.
- Hauptman Komotar, M. (2019). Global university rankings and their impact on the internationalisation of higher education. *European Journal of Education*, 54(2), 299-310.
- Heitor, M. (2015). How university global partnerships may facilitate a new era of international affairs and foster political and economic relations. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 95, 276-293.
- Hunter, D., McCallum, J., & Howes, D. (2019). Defining exploratory-descriptive qualitative (EDQ) research and considering its application to healthcare. *Journal of Nursing and Health Care*, 4(1).
- Johnes, J. (2018). University rankings: What do they really show?. *Scientometrics*, 115(1), 585-606.
- Knight, J. (2012). Concepts, rationales, and interpretive frameworks in the internationalization of higher education. *The SAGE handbook of international higher education*, 27-42.
- Knight, J. (2016). Transnational education remodeled: Toward a common TNE framework and definitions. *Journal of Studies in International Education*, 20(1), 34-47.
- Knight, J. (2018). The changing landscape of higher education internationalisation—for better or worse?. In *Perspectives on the internationalisation of higher education* (pp. 13-19). Routledge.
- Lønsmann, D. (2014). Linguistic diversity in the international workplace: Language ideologies and processes of exclusion. *Multilingua*, 33(1-2), 89-116.
- Makeeva, E., & Lopukhova, Y. (2018, May). Cross-cultural communication course as a form of internationalisation at home within Russian higher education institutions. In *Society. Integration. Education. Proceedings of the International Scientific Conference* (Vol. 1, pp. 361-372).
- Methanonphakhun, S., & Deocampo, M. F. (2016). Being an English language teacher: A narrative analysis of ten foreign teachers in Thailand. *The New English Teacher* ISSN 2985-0959 (Online), 10(1), 1-19.
- Ndaipa, C. J., Edström, K., Langa, P., & Geschwind, L. (2023). Internationalisation of the curriculum in higher education: A case from a Mozambican university. *Cogent Education*, 10(1), 2188773.
- Niehaus, E., & Williams, L. (2016). Faculty transformation in curriculum transformation: The role of faculty development in campus internationalization. *Innovative Higher Education*, 41, 59-74.
- Olcay, G. A., & Bulu, M. (2017). Is measuring the knowledge creation of universities possible?: A review of university rankings. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 123, 153-160.
- Renfors, S. M. (2021). Internationalization of the curriculum in Finnish higher education: Understanding lecturers' experiences. *Journal of Studies in International Education*, 25(1), 66-82.
- Romani-Dias, M., & Carneiro, J. (2020). Internationalization in higher education: faculty tradeoffs under the social exchange theory. *International Journal of Educational Management*, 34(3), 461-476.
- Sibawaihi, S., & Fernandes, V. (2023). Globalizing higher education through internationalization and multiculturalism: The case of Indonesia. *Higher Education Quarterly*, 77(2), 232-245.
- Snodin, N., Young, T., Thongnuan, T., Bumrungsalee, I., & Nattheeraphong, A. (2021). The migration of international academics to Thailand and their experiences of Thai higher education. *Sojourn: Journal of Social Issues in Southeast Asia*, 36(2), 225-257.
- Stukalova, I., Shishkin, A., & Stukalova, A. (2015). Internationalization of higher education: a case of Russian universities. *Economics & Sociology*, 8(1), 275.

Ulla, M. B. (2018). English language teaching in Thailand: Filipino teachers' experiences and perspectives. *Issues in Educational Research*, 28(4), 1080-1094.

Ulla, M. B., & Tarrayo, V. N. (2021). Classroom teaching or academic publishing? An investigation of Philippine doctoral academics' beliefs. *Research in Education*, 111(1), 80-88.

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